

Earth Observation Data for Seafloor Mapping: A Case Study of Croatia

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Abstract: Traditional bathymetric methods are acoustic-based systems or bathymetric LiDAR, which are able to meet the strictest survey orders for the safety of navigation defined by the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO). Although new platforms are operational (e.g. unmanned surface and aerial vehicles), traditional methods are time- and cost-consuming. With the new editions of the S-44 standards for hydrographic surveys, the IHO has acknowledged the use of bathymetric data for purposes beyond navigation safety, as new sensors (e.g., satellite-based) and sources (e.g., crowd-sourced bathymetry) have emerged. The concept of matrix parameters has been introduced to evaluate such datasets. According to the Croatian Marine Spatial Data Portal (GeoAdriatic) and the IHO, only part of Croatian navigable waters has been mapped with high accuracy and spatial resolution using traditional acoustic methods. The main aim of this paper is to analyse the use of satellite data for Earth Observation to overcome the gap in bathymetric data in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea. The results of previous research in Croatian waters were analysed in compliance with the S-44 matrix framework.

Keywords: satellite derived bathymetry; Adriatic Sea; seafloor topography; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Only a limited portion of navigable waters along the eastern Adriatic coast is covered by high-resolution multibeam bathymetric data (GeoAdriatic 2026).

Bathymetry can be derived from various satellite remote sensing (RS) data, including satellite altimetry, optical sensors (satellite-derived bathymetry, SDB), synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and satellite LiDAR bathymetry (SLB), each based on different physical principles and applicable depth ranges. Leder and Duplančić Leder (2023) concluded that bathymetric models predicted from satellite data in the shallow coastal or deep marine areas of the Republic of Croatia do not comply with the requirements of the IHO Standards for Hydrographic Surveys (S-44).

However, recent editions of S-44 introduced the matrix of parameters. The matrix is not a survey order or a standard in itself, but rather an extension intended for the classification of hydrographic data beyond the scope of navigation safety. The main objective of the paper is to evaluate the potential of satellite data for Earth Observation (EO) to address the gap in bathymetric data coverage in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea. The research is conducted in two main steps. First, a systematic review of previous studies is performed to identify digital bathymetric models (DBM) derived from satellite data

within the study area, including an analysis of their source data and methodologies. Second, their quality is assessed using a set of criteria based on the S-44 matrix.

2 Methods

The research methodology is divided into two key steps. First, a review of previous research and publicly available DBMs in the study area was conducted. The literature and datasets were identified through a systematic search of CRORIS, Google Scholar, and Web of Science Core Collection (WoS CC). The search was conducted up to the present using combinations of the keywords “bathymetry,” “seafloor mapping,” “satellite,” and “remote sensing,” always including “Adriatic.” Studies relevant to bathymetry derived from satellite data were included, while non-relevant and duplicate sources were excluded. DBMs were analysed together with their source satellite data and the methods used for bathymetry estimation. Second, a quantitative evaluation of the quality of the DBMs was performed. The following criteria from the S-44 matrix (Figure 1) were selected for quality assessment: Total Horizontal Uncertainty (THU), Total Vertical Uncertainty (TVU), Feature Detection, and Bathymetric Coverage. The parameters were derived or interpreted from the reported model characteristics, validation results, and spatial resolution of the datasets. THU was inferred from the spatial resolution of the underlying datasets and the reported positional accuracy in the original studies. TVU was derived from the reported quality parameters (e.g. root mean square error (RMSE), normalized RMSE (NRMSE), NRMSE relative to mean depth across depth intervals). In the context of RS, feature detection is related to spatial resolution, while bathymetric coverage refers to the spatial extent of the surveyed area and the percentage of area covered by valid bathymetric estimates.

Criteria	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
B	BATHYMETRY														
a	Depth THU [m]	500	200	100	50	20	15	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.35	0.1	0.05
b	Depth TVU [% of depth]	20	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.25	0.1						
c	Depth TVU "a" [m]	100	50	25	10	5	2	1	0.5	0.3	0.25	0.2	0.15	0.1	0.05
d	Depth TVU "b" Note 1	0.20	0.10	0.05	0.023	0.02	0.013	0.01	0.0075	0.004	0.002				
e	Feature Detection [m]	50	20	10	5	2	1	0.75	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.25	0.2	0.1	0.05
f	Feature Detection [% of Depth]	25	20	10	5	3	2	1	0.5	0.25					
g	Feature Search [%]	1	3	5	10	20	30	50	75	100	120	150	200	300	
h	Bathymetric Coverage [%]	1	3	5	10	20	30	50	75	100	120	150	200	300	

Figure 1. Selectable criteria for bathymetry from the IHO S-44 matrix (IHO 2024).

3 Results

A systematic review of previous research and publicly available DBMs was conducted to identify bathymetric models, their source satellite data, and methods used for bathymetry estimation in the study area. The quality of identified DBMs was assessed using the S-44 Matrix criteria.

3.1 Bathymetric models from satellite altimetry

A regional bathymetric model of the Adriatic Sea (GGM+DBM) was derived from altimeter-based free-air gravity anomalies (DTU10 model) and in situ soundings from multiple sources, including nautical charts, EMODnet 2020 DBM, and the GEBCO 1' grid. The model was computed using the gravity-geological method (GGM) (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Bathymetric model of the Adriatic Sea (GGM+DBM) (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023).

The GGM+DBM was compared with several publicly available bathymetric models, including DTU10BAT, EMODnet Bathymetry 2018, ETOPO1, GEBCO 2020, SRTM15+, and Smith and Sandwell V19.1 (SS). All of these DBMs are based on altimetry-derived bathymetry and augmented with various bathymetric datasets. The largest discrepancies between the models in the Adriatic Sea were observed along the eastern Adriatic coast, mainly due to the limitations of satellite altimetry in shallow waters and inconsistencies in the input bathymetric data. The quality of the DBMs in the Adriatic Sea was assessed against more than 3,500 soundings from nautical charts. The results showed improved accuracy of models in deeper areas, with vertical uncertainty reaching over 10% of the depth (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) relative to mean depth across depth intervals (adapted from Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023).

3.2 Optical SDB

The cut-off depth defines the maximum depth at which sunlight penetrates sufficiently to be reflected from the seafloor. The SDB potential in the Adriatic Sea was estimated based on a global Secchi Depth analysis (Hartmann et al. 2022). The analysis used satellite-derived Secchi depth (ZSD) from Copernicus Ocean Colour products as a proxy for light penetration. Along the eastern Adriatic coast, the cut-off depth ranges from 20–30 m in the central and southern regions, and from 15–20 m in the northern Adriatic. In the Šibenik Channel, in situ multibeam data indicate a cut-off depth between 20 m and 25 m (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2023).

Previous research has demonstrated the effectiveness of SDB using publicly available Sentinel-2 MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) data, primarily based on empirical approaches such as the log-band ratio (LBR) algorithm (Stumpf et al., 2003). The first case study in the Adriatic was in the Kaštela Bay. The SDB was estimated from Landsat 8/OLI (Leder and Duplančić-Leder 2017). In the coastal area of Murter Island (central Adriatic), bathymetry was estimated from Landsat 8/OLI and Sentinel-2/MSI with the LBR algorithm. Horizontal accuracy ranged from 10 to 30 m, while vertical accuracy was $\pm 2-3$ m. Although depth gradients were well captured, individual shoals were not resolved due to limited spatial resolution (Duplančić Leder and Leder 2020, Duplančić Leder et al. 2019). Bathymetry in Medulin Bay (northern Adriatic) was modelled using the LBR algorithm and Sentinel-2/MSI, yielding results consistent with previous studies.

Furthermore, the selection of atmospheric correction methods and optimal spectral band combinations has been shown to significantly improve bathymetry estimation. This was demonstrated in the Šibenik Channel using Sentinel-2/MSI and the LBR algorithm (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022) (Figure 4). The quality of the resulting DBM was evaluated using multibeam survey data.

Figure 4. SDB model of the Šibenik Channel (0–20 m), estimated from Sentinel-2/MSI (30 September 2017) using the empirical algorithm with a combination of blue, green, and red bands (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022).

3.3 Quality assessment

Based on the criteria defined in Chapter 2, the quality of previously identified DBMs is summarised in Table 1. Only the best-performing datasets for each satellite data type are included: the GGM+DBM (Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023), derived from satellite altimetry, and the SDB model of the

Table 1. Quality of DBMs expressed using criteria from S-44 matrix (adapted from Vrdoljak and Bašić 2023, Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022).

Bathymetric dataset	Source Data/Method	Horizontal uncertainty	Vertical uncertainty		Coverage/Feature detection
			Range [m]	% d	
GGM+ DBM	DTU 10 gravity anomalies and chart soundings, EMODnet, GEBCO One Minute grid/ GGM	Heterogeneous - depends on source data	0 - 20 20 - 50 50 - 100 100 - 200 +200	41 25 12 5 2	100% (1/16' grid)/kilometer scale
SDB (Šibenik channel)	Sentinel-2/MSI/LBR	10 m	0-3 3-5 5-10 10-15 15-20	52 22 20 12 10	100% up to 20 m depth/ 10 m spatial resolution
Exclusive order	Multibeam survey	1 m	a=0.15 b=0.0075 $TVU = \sqrt{a^2 + (b * d)^2}$		200% /cubic feature < 0.5 m
Order 2	Multibeam/Single-beam/Side-scan sonar survey	20m +10%d	a=1 b=0.023 $TVU = \sqrt{a^2 + (b * d)^2}$		5% /NA

Šibenik Channel (Vrdoljak and Kilić-Pamuković 2022). For comparison, the last two rows present the minimum requirements for the most and least stringent survey orders defined in S-44.

According to the S-44 matrix values (IHO 2024), the data classification string for the GGM+DBM is as follows: Bc5Bd1 (<20 m), Bc4 Bd2 (20–100 m), Bc4 Bd3 (100–200 m), Bc3 Bd10 (>200 m), and Bh9.

For the SDB model of the Šibenik Channel, the classification string is: Ba7, Bc7 Bd1 (0-5 m), Bc6 Bd2 (5-20 m), Be3, and Bh9.

The classification strings represent an encoding of the S-44 matrix criteria. Each element of the string corresponds to a specific parameter within the matrix. For example, in the notation Bc4, the letter B denotes the Bathymetry category of the S-44 matrix, while c4 specifies the particular class (row and column) within that category, as defined in Figure 1. The results indicate both datasets do not meet survey orders but demonstrate the potential for large-scale bathymetric mapping and non-navigational applications, particularly in areas where high-resolution survey data are lacking.

4 Conclusion

Evaluation of scientific research on bathymetry derived from satellite data for EO in the Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea indicates that, despite progress, gaps remain. At the moment, only a limited portion of the seabed has been mapped at high resolution using multibeam sonar systems. The remaining area is mostly covered only by coarse DBMs derived from satellite altimetry. SDB has so far been applied in sparse test areas, primarily using freely available medium-resolution satellite data (10–30 m) and empirical algorithms. Nevertheless, SDB demonstrated potential for future applications. Further research should focus on the use of high-resolution commercial satellite

missions and the use of more advanced SDB algorithms. At the same time, other satellite data such as SAR and SLB, have not yet been tested in this region. Finally, the integration of various data sources should be a direction for future work. In that way the limitations of individual data sets may be overcome.

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5 References

- Duplančić Leder, T., Leder, N., Peroš, J., 2019. Satellite Derived Bathymetry Survey Method - Example of Hramina Bay. *Transactions on maritime science*, 8(1), 99–108.
- Duplančić Leder, T., Leder, N., 2020. Optimal Conditions for Satellite Derived Bathymetry (SDB) - Case Study of the Adriatic Sea. In: *Proceedings of the FIG Working Week, Amsterdam, Netherlands, International Federation of Surveyors (FIG)*, 10–14.
- GeoAdriatic, 2026. Croatian Marine Spatial Data Portal, <https://geoadriatic.hhi.hr/>. (Accessed 29 March, 2026).
- Hartmann, K., Reithmeier, M., Knauer, K., Wenzel, J., Kleih, C.K., Heege, T., 2022. Satellite-derived bathymetry online. *International Hydrographic Review*, 28, 53–75.
- International Hydrographic Organization (IHO), 2024. S-44 Edition 6.2.0. IHO Standards for Hydrographic Surveys,

- https://iho.int/uploads/user/pubs/standards/s-44/S-44_Edition_6.2.0_adopted.pdf. (Accessed 8 May, 2026).
- Leder, N., Duplančić Leder, T., 2017. Satellite derived bathymetry – Low cost survey systems. In: Proceedings of the 7th International Maritime Science Conference (IMSC). Solin, Croatia, 516-520.
- Leder, N., Duplančić Leder, T., 2023. Application of Satellite-Derived Bathymetry in Hydrographic Activity of the Republic of Croatia. Proceedings of the 10th International Maritime Science Conference (IMSC). Solin, Croatia, 336-346.
- Stumpf, R.P., Holderied, K., 2003. Determination of Water Depth with High-Resolution Satellite Imagery over Variable Bottom Types. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 48(1), 547-556.
- Vrdoljak, Lj., Kilić Pamuković, J., 2022. Assessment of Atmospheric Correction Processors and Spectral Bands for Satellite-Derived Bathymetry Using Sentinel-2 Data in the Middle Adriatic. *Hydrology*, 9, 215.
- Vrdoljak, Lj., Bašić, T., 2023. Bathymetry Estimation from Satellite Altimeter-Derived Gravity Data. In: *Satellite Altimetry - Theory, Applications and Recent Advances*, IntechOpen.